

A potentiometric sensor based on heterogeneous inorganic chelating ion exchanger for the determination of Al^{III} ions

Himanshu Agarwal, Chandan Kumar Singh and Sulekh Chandra*

Department of Chemistry, Zakir Husain College (University of Delhi), J. L. Nehru Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : himan_007@rediffmail.com

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Preparation and applications of a novel long life aluminium ion membrane electrode sensor based on heterogeneous inorganic chelating ion exchanger i.e. tetracycline sorbed tin(IV) molybdophosphate (TC-TMP) are described. The poly(vinyl chloride) matrix membrane electrode of the resin exhibits good potentiometric response for Al^{III} over a wide concentration range (10^{-5} to 10^{-1} M) with a slope of 22.6 mV/decade. The sensor response is stable for at least 2 years. The sensor offers the advantages of significantly high thermal stability and resistivity towards redox reagents and strong mineral acids. Good selectivity for Al^{III} in comparison with alkaline, transition and heavy metal ions and minimal interference are caused by Hg²⁺ and Ba²⁺, which are also known to interference with other aluminum membrane sensor. The proposed sensor displays a useful analytical response with excellent reproducibility, good precision, low detection limit and applicability use in aqueous solutions of pH 2–8 and in partially non-aqueous medium with up to 10% (v/v) organic contents. The proposed electrode has been utilized as an end point indicator electrode in potentiometric titrations of Al^{III} with EDTA and applied successfully for the determination of aluminum in real samples also.

Inorganic ion exchangers are characterized by high thermal stability and resistivity towards strong oxidizing agents and mineral acids. Preparation, characterization and uses of several inorganic ion exchangers in nuclear strategies have been reported¹. However, a limited number of membrane sensors using inorganic ion exchangers² have been developed and most of these suffer from poor selectivity³. In the present study, a heterogeneous inorganic chelating ion exchange resin, tetracycline sorbed tin(IV) molybdophosphate (TC-TMP) is employed as an electroactive material for the construction of a novel aluminum ion membrane sensor. The proposed membrane electrode exhibits good selectivity, fast response, relatively short lifetime and wide working concentration range for the determination of aluminum. In addition to these, the sensor also offers the advantage of thermal stability, simplicity, sensitivity, reliability, low cost and long life.

Results and discussion

Characterization of the sensor membranes is essential to correlate the movement of ions in the membrane with the potential generating across it. The properties of the membrane⁴ viz. water content (27.01%), porosity (0.0035), thickness (0.42 mm), electrolyte absorption (32 μ g) and swelling (0.25 mm) reveals that the membrane is of least porosity and swelling. The electrolyte absorption reveals that the diffusion will take place through the exchange sites

present in the membrane phase. So this membrane is expected to be selective in their response to a particular ion, hence leading to high selectivity of the membrane electrode.

Different calibration of Al^{III}-selective (TC-TMP)-PVC membrane electrode sensor with different concentrations of the internal aluminum filling solution (0.1, 1×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-3} , 1×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-5} M Al(NO₃)₃) were tested. The results indicated that the use of 1×10^{-5} M Al(NO₃)₃ as internal filling solution gave an optimum calibration slope.

The potential displayed by the Al^{III}-selective (TC-TMP)-PVC membrane electrode sensor for consecutive measurements of 1×10^{-5} – 1×10^{-1} M aluminum solutions once in every week over a period of 2 years did not vary by more than ± 1 mV, provided that the sensor was stored in distilled water or 1×10^{-5} M Al^{III} and the internal filling solution was changed every three months (Fig. 1). The slope of the calibration curve was 22.6 mV/decade for Al^{III} concentration. The limit of detection, as evaluated from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph was 1×10^{-5} M.

The pH dependence of the membrane sensor was tested over the pH range 1–13 at 1×10^{-2} M Al^{III} concentration. Potentials remain constant from pH 2–8, beyond which a gradual change in potential is observed. A sharp change in potentials at lower pH values (<2) appears to be due to interference caused by H⁺ ions, while at high pH values (>8)

Fig. 1. Calibration curve of Al^{3+} -selective (TC-TMP)-PVC based membrane electrode.

may be attributed to hydrolysis of Al^{III} ions.

The electrode response for Al^{III} as a representative case was also studied in different mixed-organic media, e.g. ethanol and acetone (2–10%) (v/v) (Table 1). The calibration plot is plotted in each case and the slope of the curve is compared with the aqueous system. It is observed that the

Table 1. Effect of non-aqueous solvents on calibration curve of Al^{III} -selective (TC-TMP)-PVC membrane electrode

Solvent	Composition % (v/v)	Slope (mV/decade concentration change)
Water	–	22.6
Ethanol	2	22.6
Ethanol	5	22.6
Ethanol	10	22.3
Acetone	2	22.6
Acetone	5	22.6
Acetone	10	22.1

electrode is stable in ethanol and acetone upto 10%, but the matrix swelled continuously in higher proportions of ethanol and acetone after a few hours. The responses of the electrode in 5 and 10% ethanol and acetone-water systems is steady from few hours to few days after which the potential deviates (Table 2).

Calibration graphs were constructed at test solution temperatures (25, 35, 45, 55, 60 and 65°C) for Al^{III} -electrode. The slope usable concentration range, the standard cell potential (E°) and response time of the electrode corresponding to each temperature are reported in Table 3. It is clear that the electrode has a good Nernstian response in the temperature range 25–60°C. For the determination of the isothermal coefficient (dE°/dt) of the cell, the standard cell potential (E°) at different temperatures were obtained from the calibration graphs as the intercepts at $p^{\text{Al}} = 0$ and plotted versus ($t-25$), where t is temperature of the test solution. The resultant plot is a straight line.

The slopes of the straight line obtained represent⁵ the isothermal coefficient of the cell, amounting to 8.3×10^{-4} V/°C, revealing a practically good thermal stability of the cell.

In addition to the Nernstian behaviour, linear range and detection limit, the selectivity of the membrane sensor for Al^{III} ions over the other metal cations is also of fundamental importance. Thus, the selectivity of the membrane electrode was tested by its potentials response measurements in the presence of a wide variety of cations including alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. The selectivity coefficients $K_{\text{Al}}^{\text{Pot}}$, were evaluated graphically by the mixed

Table 2. Response time for non-aqueous solvents (Al^{III} -selective membrane electrode)

Sl. no.	Time (h)	Potential (mV) 10% ethanol	Potential (mV) 5% ethanol	Potential (mV) 10% acetone	Potential (mV) 5% acetone
1.	0	41	33	54	40
2.	5	37	33	40	40
3.	10	33	27	37	40
4.	15	26	24	33	40
5.	20	23	21	31	38
6.	25	21	17	24	34
7.	30	20	15	22	28
8.	35	18	14	20	28
9.	40	17	11	19	28
10.	45	16	11	18	28
11.	50	15	11	18	28
12.	55	15	11	18	28
13.	60	15	11	18	28
14.	65	15	11	18	28

Table 3. Performance characteristics of Al^{III}-selective (TC-TMP)-PVC membrane electrode at different temperatures

Temperature (°C)	Slope (mV/decade)	Usable concentration range (M)	E° (mv)	Response time (s)
25	22.6	2.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –4.0 × 10 ⁻³	250	≤30
35	22.8	2.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –2.5 × 10 ⁻³	266	≤30
45	23.3	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁶ –2.3 × 10 ⁻³	272	≤32
55	23.9	6.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻³	276	≤25
60	24.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.5 × 10 ⁻³	282	≤23
65	27.1	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	290	≤21

solution method⁶. Here, the fixed concentration of interfering ions (1 × 10⁻⁵ M) was used against the varying concentration of the primary ions.

The fixed interference method is based on the semi-empirical Nilolsky-Eisenman eq. (1).

$$E_{ISE} = E^{\circ} \pm \frac{RT}{Z_A F} \ln \left(a_A + \sum K_{A,B}^{pot} (a_B)^{Z_A/Z_B} \right) \quad (1)$$

It is quite well known that the above equation works well in modelling the non-specific response of a membrane when the ions under investigation have the same charge, i.e. Z_A = Z_B, but the same is not well suited for ions having different charges i.e. Z_A ≠ Z_B. Coefficients are either deceptively large or small depending on whether the ion of higher charge is considered as primary or interfering species.

However, it is seen that Pb²⁺, which is a serious interference with other aluminum sensors does not cause any interference at all with the present, but Ba²⁺ and Hg²⁺ cause interference to some extent (Table 4).

Table 4. Selectivity coefficients (K_{ij}) values of Al^{III} sensor based on (TC-TMP)-PVC membrane for different cations

Metal ion	Selectivity coefficients values (K _{ij})
Mg ²⁺	0.56 × 10 ⁻¹
Ca ²⁺	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹
Sr ²⁺	0.19 × 10 ⁻¹
Ba ²⁺	3.04 × 10 ⁻¹
Cd ²⁺	0.05 × 10 ⁻¹
Hg ²⁺	6.25 × 10 ⁻¹
Zn ²⁺	0.36 × 10 ⁻²
Cu ²⁺	0.22 × 10 ⁻²
Co ²⁺	0.14 × 10 ⁻²
Ni ²⁺	0.14 × 10 ⁻²
Mn ²⁺	2.21 × 10 ⁻³
Pb ²⁺	3.56 × 10 ⁻³
Fe ³⁺	5.00 × 10 ⁻³
Bi ³⁺	1.25 × 10 ⁻²

The proposed Al^{III} membrane sensor was found to work well under laboratory conditions. It was successfully applied to the titration of (1 × 10⁻² M) EDTA solution with Al^{III} ion solution and the resulting titration curve is shown in Fig. 2. However a necessary adjustment of pH was made before adding the titrant. A sharp inflection point and perfect stoichiometry are noteworthy features of this titration.

The proposed electrode was applied to the determination of aluminum in antacid tablets and drinking water. For

Fig. 2. EDTA titration curve for (TC-TMP)-PVC based membrane electrode.

preparation of samples 5 tablets was finely crushed and dissolved in nitric acid and diluted to 25 ml by distilled water. Neutralize 25 ml of the prepared solution to congo red paper with 20% NaOH solution and added 75 ml of distilled water and finally 50 ml of 0.05 M of EDTA. Mixed, heat on a water bath for thirty minutes and finally cooled in order to obtain the clear solution⁷. Two samples were prepared by spiking suitable amounts of aluminum nitrate into drinking water. The aluminum concentration of the samples was potentiometrically determined with the electrode by the calibration plot method. Aluminum was also determined

by flame atomic absorption spectrometry. The results are shown in Table 5 and found in agreement.

Table 5. Determination of aluminum in real samples

Samples	Aluminum concentration $\times 10^{-5} M$		
	Prepared	Found by ISE	Found by AAS
Tablets	–	6.54 ± 0.2	6.50 ± 0.1
Drinking water (a)	4.62	4.52 ± 0.1	4.58 ± 0.2
(b)	6.02	6.0 ± 0.1	6.0 ± 0.1

Experimental

All chemicals used were analytical grade unless otherwise specified. In addition, all standard solutions and buffers were prepared with double-distilled water. Standard aluminum ion working solutions (10^{-1} – $10^{-7} M$) were prepared by dilution of appropriate aliquots of 1 M stock aluminum nitrate.

Preparation of tin(IV) molybdophosphate (TMP) ion exchanger :

The exchanger, tin(IV) molybdophosphate (TMP) was prepared as reported⁸ by mixing acidic solution of 0.1 M stannic chloride, 0.1 M sodium molybdate and 0.1 M sodium orthophosphate in a volume ratio of 2 : 1 : 1 at pH 1. The ion exchanger was converted into H⁺ form by treatment with 1.0 M HNO₃ for 24 h.

Sorption of tetracycline hydrochloride on tin(IV) molybdophosphate ion exchanger :

Sorption of tetracycline hydrochloride on TMP was done according to the procedure previously described⁹ as follows : TMP in H⁺ form was heated with 200 cm³ of boiling DIW for 1 h to remove impurities. It was decanted and shaken with 100 cm³ of 0.1 % (v/v) tetracycline hydrochloride for 4 h and left for overnight. The tetracycline hydrochloride solution was then decanted to obtain reddish brown tetracycline sorbed tin(IV) molybdophosphate (TC-TMP). It was washed 2–3 times to remove the excess tetracycline hydrochloride. Finally the product was dried at $40 \pm 2^\circ C$.

Preparation of poly(vinyl chloride) membrane :

The electroactive material required for the preparation of membrane ion selective electrode (MISE) was of the heterogeneous inorganic chelating ion exchanger i.e. TC-TMP (0.2 g) mixed with PVC (0.17 g) in 6 mL tetrahydrofuran (THF)¹⁰. The resulting solution was poured onto a glass ring with an inner diameter of 30 mm resting on a smooth glass plate and THF was allowed to evaporate un-

der 48 h standing at room temperature.

Potential measurements :

All potential measurements were made with an Equiptronic-India digital potentiometer [Model No : EQ 602] with a saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. The response of the sensor for aluminum(III) ions was examined by measuring the electrochemical cell by setting up the following electrochemical cell assembly :

External saturated calomel electrode (SCE)	Test solution	Membrane	Internal solution	Internal saturated calomel electrode (SCE)
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